
CONTENT VALIDITY OF MATHEMATICS MULTIPLE CHOICE TEST ITEMS USED IN 2021 BASIC EDUCATION CERTIFICATE EXAMINATION (BECE) AND ITS IMPLICATIONS ON QUALITY EDUCATION IN DELTA STATE.

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Abstract: *The Study investigated the Contributions of the Mathematics Multiple Choice Test Items used in 2021 BECE Examination in Delta State in the Achievement of the Basic Education Curriculum Objectives. Three research questions and two Hypotheses guided the study. Delphi research design was adopted in selecting 30 experienced Mathematics teachers who assisted the researcher to develop: the observed table of specification from the 2021 Mathematics objective test and the expected table of specification from the BECE Mathematic Curriculum. Purposive Sampling was used in selecting the 60 objective questions used for the 2021 BECE which represent the sample size for the study. The results of the table of specifications were analysed using goodness of fit chi-square and t-test statistics at 0.05 alpha level of significance respectively. The findings from the data analyzed showed that BECE Mathematics test lack content validity because questions used in the examination did not covered all the topics outlined in the curriculum. The questions also fail to measure the higher order cognitive domain. The Study recommended that for quality basic education in the State, questions used in BECE examination should cover all the contents in the curriculum as well as emphasised the higher order cognitive processes. It was concluded that BECE test items, in their current form, have not helped in the achievement of quality education.*

Keywords: Quality Education, Content validity, Basic Education, and Mathematics Curriculum

Introduction

Education is the process of achieving the desired intellectual, moral, physical and emotional changes among children in order for them to be responsible and useful people in the society. It involves the acquisition of skills, knowledge and competencies required for a successful living in order to be self-dependent, solve complex problems as well as to contribute positively to the growth and development of the society. The advent of European Missionaries in Nigeria brought about Western Education. Prior to this time, there was no official assessment or examination for assessing change in behaviours due to teaching and learning. . The two forms of Examination introduced by the Missionaries were standardized and non- standardized. The non- standardized examinations otherwise known as internal exams are tests developed and conducted within the domain of the institution (Teacher made Test), e.g. terminal and Promotions Examinations conducted by teachers, On the other hand, Standardized tests otherwise known as external Examinations are tests developed and conducted by external examination bodies (Omorogories & Iri-Aghodo ,2016). For example, Examinations conducted by State Ministry of Education, National Examination Council of Nigeria (NECO), Joint Admission and Matriculation Board (JAMB), West African Examination COUNCIL (WAEC), National Business and Technical Examination Board (NABTEB) , Basic Education Certificate Examination(BECE), among others.

According to the National Policy on Education (2014), education is formally divided into three stages: primary, secondary and tertiary education. The basic education, which comprises the primary and junior secondary stages of education, was introduced in Nigeria in September, 1988 (FRN, 2004). Furthermore, the Federal Government through the Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC) established and initiated the 9-year Basic Education Curriculum (BEC) in schools by re-arranging all existing primary and junior secondary school curriculum to achieve the main objective of the UBE Programme. The idea of the 9-year Basic Education Curriculum is to help students in acquiring appropriate levels of literacy, numeracy, manipulative, communicative and life-skills in addition to civil values and morals required for laying a solid foundation for a life time learning as a requirement for Scientific and Philosophical Reasoning (Orluweme, 2017).

Review of Literature

A test is a valid and reliable instrument used in assessing learning outcomes. It is said to be valid if it measures what it is supposed to measure (Moyinoluwa, 2015). Validity is the most important aspect of test development without which the entire testing is a waste of time. Therefore, it is a compulsory task upon any test developer to follow strictly the procedures of ensuring the validity of any given test (Okwori, 2019).

Achievement test is a type of test used in determining the extent to which students have covered a given content are in line with the cognitive domain (Osadebe, 2018). It can be in the form of objective or essay. One form of the objective test is the multiple choice test which is the focus of this study. In this form, questions are asked and testees are expected to respond by ticking the correct answer from the list of the given options (Lok, 2021).

Multiple-choice testing is one of the most enduring and successful forms of educational assessment that remains in practice today. Ani (2014), asserted that multiple choice questions can be used in assessing both the higher and lower order of cognitive domain. Multiple-choice items are efficient to administer, they are easy to score objectively, they can be used to sample wide range content, they require a relatively short time to administer (Rodriguez, 2016). According to Downing (2006), in his seminal chapter in the

Handbook of test development, stated that selected-response items like multiple choice, are the most appropriate item format for measuring cognitive achievement or ability, especially higher-order cognitive skills, such as problem solving, synthesis and evaluation. He asserted that the item format is both useful and appropriate for creating exams intended to measure a broad range of knowledge, ability or cognitive skills across many domains.

According to Kirkendall, Grubar and Johnson (1987, cited in Etaga, 2013)

Multiple choice the most useful type of objective test, multiple choice item can be used to measure both simple and complex learning outcome, for example, it can be used to measure knowledge of terminologies, specific facts, principles, methods, procedures, etc. It is also to apply facts and principles, effect relationship (p.71).

Therefore, multiple-choice tests are of considerably widespread use as a means of objective measurements. The main reason behind such popularity is the many advantages associated with multiple-choice test items.

The need to examine the characteristics (validity) of multiple-objective test is more important than ever before, since it is the most commonly used form of test by examination bodies. Psychometric properties are characteristics of tests and other measures of human characteristics that identify and describe attributes of an instrument, such as its reliability, validity and appropriateness for use in a particular circumstance. According to Okerinde (2010), the psychometric properties of every good multiple-choice test items include validity, reliability, difficulty index and discrimination index. Validity is the extent to which a test measures what it is supposed to measure. It is the most critical and crucial aspect of test development that focused on what and how well a test measures what it was designed to measure.

Table of Specification

Table of specification is the most widely used method in obtaining content of a test (Dickson, et al. 2020). Table of specification serves as a crucial guide for item development and showcases the achievement domain been measured. The essence of table of specification is to identify the achievement domain being assessed and to ensure that a fair and representative sample of questions appears on the test. Table of specification help to avoid overlapping in the construction of the test items, helps to determine the weighting of learning outcomes regarding content area and ensures that justice is done to all aspects of the course (Dickson, et al. 2019). However, a table of specification is no guarantee that the errors in the test item will be corrected, such a blueprint help improve the content validity of teacher - made test (Quansah & Amoako, 2018). In preparing a table of specification, the test developer must first list all contents taught in the course, assign corresponding numerical weighting to each topic, decide on the item format, decide on the number of items to be constructed for each topic and decide on the type of question under the different cognitive learning domain.

Quality Education is a system of education that enables the achievement of educational goals and objectives. It involves the acquisition of appropriate skills, knowledge and competencies required for the well-being of an individual in order to contribute positively to the growth and development of the society. Thus, how developed a country is, is a function of the quality of her education. According to Odili (2019), quality education is an

educational process that guarantees acquisition of knowledge, competencies and skills for living. It creates enabling environment in terms of input, process and product that ensures acquisition of abilities for critical thinking and life-long learning. Furthermore, Arundhati et.al (2016) noted that quality education includes: technology modules done, lecturing methodology, programme enrolled attachments, co-curricular activities, qualification, learning resources, appraisal towards educational and opinion among others.

The essence of education is to acquit and empower learners with appropriate knowledge, skills and competencies. Therefore, it is important that one acquires education that is of quality. This is because, what a person acquires, directly affects their mindset, philosophy and lifestyle. Odili (2019) noted that education in Nigeria cannot be judged as being of high quality. This is probably the reason why the goals of Basic Education have not been achieved in Nigeria. The lack of access to high Quality Education is the major reason why politicians, high business men and women and top civil servants send their children abroad for studies. Furthermore, UNICEF (2019) asserted that Nigeria has a low educational access. Thus, quality Education is required for the attainment of the Basic Education goals in order to produce people who can solve meaningful problems in the society.

Research Questions

1. How well do the Mathematics objective test items used in 2021 BECE reflect the Mathematics curriculum?
2. What are the areas of mismatch between the observed and the expected tables of specifications in Mathematics BECE examination in 2021?
3. What cognitive order skill does the Mathematics object test items used in 2021 BECE measure most?

Hypotheses

H₁: There is no significant difference between the expected table of specification and the observed table in 2021 Mathematics BECE.

H₂: There is no significant difference between upper and lower order cognitive Mathematics test items used in 2021 BECE.

Methodology

The design for this study was Delphi. The questions used for 2021 Basic Education Certificate Examination in Delta State which was made up of 5 theories and 60 Multiple Questions was the Population of the study. The 60 Multiple Choice was purposively sampled for this study. The observed and expected table of specifications developed with the assistance of the 30 experts were analysed using goodness of fit chi-square and t-test statistics at $P \leq 0.05$ alpha level of Significance.

Results and discussion

Table 1: OBSERVED TABLE OF SPECIFICATION FOR 2021

Contents	Knowledge 43%	Comprehension 22%	Application 20%	Analysis 7%	Synthesis 5%	Evaluation 3%	Total 100%
Arithmetic 41%	11	5	5	2	1	2	25
Algebra 21%	5	3	3	1	1	-	13
Trigonometry 17%	4	2	2	1	1	-	10
Geometry 12%	3	2	1	1	-	-	7
Variation 4%	1	1	-	-	-	-	2
Probability & Statistics 5%	2	1	-	-	-	-	3
Total	26	13	12	4	3	2	60

Table 2: Expected table of specification.

Branches of Mathematics	Knowledge 20 %	Comprehension 15%	Application 20 %	Analysis 20 %	Synthesis 15 %	Evaluation 10 %	Total 100 %
Arithmetic 47 %	6	4	6	5	4	3	28
Algebra 22 %	3	2	3	2	2	1	13
Trigonometry 6 %	-	1	1	1	1	-	4
Geometry 16 %	2	1	2	2	1	1	9
Variation 1 %	-	-	-	1	-	-	1
Probability & Statistics 8 %	1	1	1	1	1	1	5
Total 100 %	12	9	12	12	9	6	60

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between the expected table of specification and the observed table in 2021 Mathematics BECE.

Table 3: The Goodness of fit of the Expected table of specification and the Observed used 2021 BECE

Variables	N	Chi-square	Df	P-value	Decision
Observed	60	35.60	5	0.000	Reject
Expected	60				

The result in the table 3 shows the X^2 –value of 15.60 and p-value of 0.000. Testing the null hypothesis at an alpha level of 0.05, the p-value of 0.000 is less than the alpha level of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between the expected table of specification and the observed in 2021 BECE is rejected. This means that there is a significant difference in the mathematics objective test items used in 2021 BECE in Delta State and the objectives of the curriculum.

Research Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between upper and lower order cognitive Mathematics test items used in 2021 BECE.

Table 4: The paired t- test statistics for higher and lower order cognitive objective test items used 2021 Mathematics BECE.

Cognitive order	N	Mean	SD	Mean difference	Df	t	p-value (2-tailed)	Decision
Higher	20	3.3334	3.44480	3.33333	5	4.385	0.007	Reject
Lower	40	6.6667	5.04645					

Table 4 revealed the t –value of 4.385 and p-value of 0.007. Testing the null hypothesis at an alpha level of 0.05, the p-value of 0.007 is less than the alpha level of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between upper and lower order cognitive test items used in 2021 Mathematics BEC is rejected. This means that the Mathematics objective test items used for lower and higher cognitive skills differ significantly in 2021 BECE in Delta State.

Furthermore, as shown in the table 4.16 above, the lower cognitive test with the mean of 6.67, S.D =5.05 has a mean difference of 3.33 over the higher order test that has a mean of 3.33, S.D =3.44. The mean difference of 3.33 was found to be significant at $p \leq 0.05$ level of significance. The conclusion was drawn that the effect size of 3.33 which was in favour of lower cognitive test indicates that more items was allocated to the lower order domain in Delta State 2021 BECE.

Discussion

As shown in table 1, there is a significant difference in the mathematics objective test items used in 2021 BECE in Delta State and the objectives of the curriculum. This finding supports the work of Chinelo, B.O. and Osaze, D.E. (2016) that Junior Secondary School Mathematics test items have moderate internal consistency reliability and low in content validity. The low content validity in BECE may be due to the fact that BECE do not use test experts in the construction of Mathematics test items. Furthermore, as also revealed in table 2, there is a significant difference between upper and lower order cognitive Mathematics test items used in 2021 BECE. This finding is in line with the study of Robin, G. et al. (2013) which revealed that that questions designed by examiners to assess students’ progress in a particular unit or curriculum were not given proper weights in the examination papers.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study; Delta State ministry of education should ensure that the Basic Education Certificate Examination test items are constructed in line with the Basic Education Curriculum in the various subjects. This will help to achieve the goals of Basic Education spelt out in the National Policy on Education as revised in 2014. Also, that State Ministries of Education should place more emphasis on higher cognitive tests to enable students acquire higher order skills required for quality education and their survival in the society.

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